

Stereospecific β -lactam formation via Staudinger cycloaddition derived from ferrocenyl imines

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Stereospecific synthesis of a few 3,4-disubstitued β -lactams derived from polyaromatic ferrocenyl imines is achieved following Staudinger cycloaddition reaction. The exclusive formation of *trans*- β -lactams is observed. The stereochemistry of these resulting β -lactams formation reaction is unprecedented.

Keywords: β -Lactams, cycloaddition, ferrocene, polyaromatic amines, unprecedented stereochemistry.

Introduction

The use of β -lactams in our daily life is very significant because of their many medicinal values. Consequently, research on the synthesis of diverse β -lactams has received considerable attention. We have been actively engaged in the synthesis of anticancer β -lactams and related compounds for many years. In continuation of our exploratory research in this area, we describe stereospecific synthesis of a few *trans* 3,4-disubstitued β -lactams using polyaromatic ferrocenyl imines by Staudinger cycloaddition reaction.

The β -lactams have had a variety of clinical applications. In addition to penicillins and cephalosporins, a number of biologically relevant enzymes have been targeted by these types of compounds.

The usefulness of effective β -lactam antibiotics and β -lactamase inhibitors has motivated chemists and scientists to design and synthesize new β -lactams. β -Lactams have also served as starting compounds in the synthesis of various heterocyclic compounds of biological importance. Hydroxy β -lactam derivatives have been the key materials in the semi-synthesis of paclitaxel (Taxol) and docetaxel (Taxotere). The medicinal application of β -lactams as thera-

peutic agents for lowering plasma cholesterol levels has been published^{1a-f}.

Results and discussion

The Staudinger cycloaddition reaction extensively explored for the synthesis of β -lactams^{2a-c}. The formation of β -lactams depends on a number of factors. The substituents present in the imine and acid chloride, temperature, solvent and the conditions of the reactions have enormous effects in controlling the stereochemistry of the products^{3a-c}. The reaction of oxygen- and nitrogen-containing acid chloride with diaryl imine mainly produces *cis*- β -lactams. In contrast, the reaction of polyaromatic imines with identical acid chlorides produces *trans* β -lactams. Some of the *trans* β -lactams have

Scheme 1. Synthesis of N-polyaromatic substituted 3-ferrocenyl imines.

demonstrated excellent anticancer activity^{4a-d}. The anticancer activities of *cis* β -lactams has also been studied since 2000 at the University of Texas M. D. Anderson Cancer Center. It may be stated that we are one of the most active pioneers in this field of anticancer β -lactam research. Because of the prominent and consistent anticancer activities against different types of cancer cell lines and NCI cancer cell panels, synthetic studies of these types of compounds have great values. Of interest, a few selected compounds are active against cancer cells *in vivo* with appropriate therapeutic index and minimum toxicities.

successfully at high temperature using toluene as the solvent.

This current study describes the synthesis of β -lactams using ferrocenyl imines and acid chloride in the presence of triethyl amine^{5,6}.

Reaction of ferrocene aldehyde (**1**) with several polyaromatic compounds (**2a-f**) in toluene under reflux conditions produced imine **3** after 72 h using a Dean-Stark water separator (Scheme 1). The imine **3** was then reacted with acid chloride **4** at 0°C-room temperature and a single *trans*

Although, numerous benzene derived aldehydes have been used as the starting materials for the preparation of imines the use of ferrocene aldehyde as one the components for imine preparation is limited. In fact, preparation of imine with polyaromatic amino compound and 2-ferrocene aldehyde is not known except from our own study. Polyaromatic amines are not sufficiently nucleophilic to react with ferrocene aldehyde. However, imines are prepared

β -lactam **5** was obtained in 70% yield (Scheme 2). No *cis* β -lactam **6** was formed. This result was similar with that obtained when an aromatic phenyl or substituted phenyl group was present in the imine component. In a similar way, acid **7** on cycloaddition with imines **3a-e** produced exclusively *trans*-phthalimido β -lactams **8a-e**. No *cis*-phthalimido β -lactams **9a-e** was formed (Scheme 3)^{7,8}.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of β -lactam via Staudinger ketene-imine [2+2] cycloaddition reaction.

Table 1

Entry	Amine	R	3-Ferrocenyl imine	Time (h)	Yield ^a (%)
1	2a	1-Naphthylamine	3a	12	80
2	2b	1-Aminoanthracene	3b	24	75
3	2c	6-Aminochrysene	3c	48	70
4	2d	9-Aminophenanthrene	3d	24	75
5	2e	11-Dibenzofullerene	3e	48	70
6	2f	1-Aminopyrene	3f	48	70

Table 2

Entry	3	R ¹	R	5+6	Diestereomeric ^a	Time (h)	Yield ^b (%)
1	3a	OAc	1-Naphthylamine	5a+6a	100:0	12	80
2	3b	OAc	1-Aminoanthracene	5b+6b	100:0	24	75
3	3c	OAc	6-Aminochrysene	5c+6c	100:0	24	70
4	3d	OAc	9-Aminophenanthrene	5d+6d	100:0	24	75
5	3e	OAc	11-Aminodibenzofullerene	5e+6e	100:0	24	70
6	3f	OBn	1-Naphthylamine	5f+5f	100:0	24	75
7	3g	OBn	1-Aminoanthracene	5g+6g	100:0	24	70
8	3h	OBn	6-Aminochrysene	5h+6h	100:0	24	70
9	3i	OBn	9-Aminophenanthrene	5i+6i	100:0	24	75
10	3j	OBn	11-Aminodibenzofullerene	5j+6j	100:0	24	70

Table 3

Entry	3	R ¹	R	8+9	Diestereomeric ^a	Time (h)	Yield ^b (%)
1	3a	Nphth	1-Naphthylamine	8a+9a	100:0	12	75
2	3b	Nphth	1-Aminoanthracene	8b+9b	100:0	24	65
3	3c	Nphth	6-Aminochrysene	8c+9c	100:0	24	70
4	3d	Nphth	9-Aminophenanthrene	8d+9d	100:0	24	75
5	3e	Nphth	11-Aminodibenzofullerene	8e+9e	100:0	24	60

Therefore, diverse C-4 ferrocenyl *trans* β -lactams with a C-3 substituted amide, ester and ether are available from this study. The results observed in this present investigation support our earlier results. The formation of *trans* compounds can be explained through an isomerization of the enolate as describe earlier^{1,2}. The ferrocenyl unit at the C-centre of the imines behaves like an aromatic or substituted group rather than a conjugated aromatic group (for example, cinnamyl group). It has been found that conjugated system at C-2 of the imines can alter the stereochemical distribution of the β -lactam formation by not adopting ketene-imine cyclization pathways. Probably the iron-atom present in ferrocene inhibits to stabilize the intermediate that produces *cis* β -lactams. These β -lactams are similar to the anticancer compounds reported from our laboratory. The presence of the iron-containing group in these β -lactams is of interest since they can alter the biological profile. An availability of these new compounds may prove to be useful for structure-activity study. N-Polyaromatic imines highly favour the *trans* selec-

tivity to furnish the *trans* β -lactam exclusively. This also perturbed isomerization along sigma bond in the transition state. It has been demonstrated that the stereoselectivity depends on the structure of the imine, acid-chloride, order of addition of the reagents, solvent, temperature, bases and many other conditions. This is also depends on the mode of addition of reagent during reaction.

General Experimental procedure

Scheme 3. Synthesis of N-phthalimido β -lactam via Staudinger ketene-imine [2+2] cycloaddition reaction.

A representative experimental procedure is given below. A solution consisting of acid chloride (1.5 mmol) in dichloromethane (2 mL) was added to imine (1 mmol) and triethylamine (3 mmol). The reaction mixture was then stirred at room temperature for 24 h, washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (10 mL), dilute hydrochloric acid (10%, 10 mL), brine (10 mL), dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated to obtain the crude product. Proton NMR was performed to calculate the ratio of the isomeric β -lactams. The formation of only the *trans* isomer (coupling constant of the C-3 and C-4 hydrogens was approximately 1–3 Hz) was observed. The pure *trans* product was then obtained via column chromatography over silica gel using ethyl acetate-hexanes (1:4) as the solvent. Some of the compounds were isolated as crystalline solid.

Conclusion

The stereochemical results with ferrocenyl imines follow our earlier observation with diaryl imines. These compounds are new. No attempts have been made to prepare these types of compounds despite huge interest in β -lactam research. Research in this area has opened up enormous possibilities. We will disclose these results in the future.

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References

- (a) B. K. Banik, Ed., *Top. Heterocycl. Chem.*, Springer, 2010, **22**, 1; (b) B. K. Banik, *Top. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2012, **30**, 1; (c) I. Banik and B. K. Banik, Ed., Springer, 2012, **88**, 781; (d) B. K. Banik, Ed., Springer, 2017, 1; (e) P. T. Parvatkar, P. S. Parameswaran and B. K. Banik, Ed., Springer, 2017, 253; (f) S. Basu, B. K. Banik, Ed., Springer, 2017, 285.
- (a) Y.-R. Zhang, L. He, X. Wu, P. L. Shao and S. Ye, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 277; (b) B. L. Hodous and G. C. Fu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 1578; (c) B. Musio, F. Mariani, E. P. Śliwiński, M. A. Kabeshov, H. Odajima and S. V. Ley, *Synthesis*, 2016, **48**, 3515.
- (a) Fernando P. Cossio, Ana Arrieta and Miguel A. Sierra, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2008, **41**, 925; (b) Cody Ross Pitts and Thomas Lectka, *Chem. Rev.*, 2014, **114**, 7930; (c) B. K. Banik, B. Lecea, A. Arrieta, A. Cozar and F. P. Cossio, *Angew. Chem.*, 2007 **46**, 3028.
- R. V. J. Chari, *Adv. Drug. Delivery Rev.*, 1998, **31**, 89; (b) B. K. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2001, **46**, 593; (c) I. Banik, F. F. Becker and B. K. Banik, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **12**, 12; (d) B. K. Banik, F. F. Becker and I. Banik, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **13**, 2523; (e) B. K. Banik, I. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **13**, 3611.
- (a) B. K. Banik, Ed., 2010, **22**, 1; (b) B. K. Banik, Ed., "Top. Heterocycl. Chem.", Springer, 2012, **30**, 1; (c) I. Banik, B. K. Banik, Springer, 2012, **88**, 781; (d) B. K. Banik, Ed., Springer, 2017, **1**, 419; (e) P. T. Parvatkar, P. S. Parameswaran and B. K. Banik, Ed., Springer, 2017, 253; (f) S. Basu, B. K. Banik, Ed., Springer, 2017, 285; (g) B. K. Banik, "CRC Book", 2013, 31.
- (a) I. Banik, F. F. Becker and B. K. Banik, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **46**, 12; (b) B. K. Banik, F. F. Becker and I. Banik, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**, 2523; (c) B. K. Banik, *Curr. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**; (d) B. K. Banik, I. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **13**, 3611; (e) B. K. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Mol. Med. Rep.*, 2010, **3**, 315; (f) B. K. Banik, I. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 846; (g) B. K. Banik, *International Innovation*, 2011, 50; (h) B. K. Banik, *International Innovation*, 2012, 114; (i) B. K. Banik, S. Samajdar and F. F. Becker, *Molecular Medicine Reports*, 2010, **3**, 319.
- (a) B. K. Banik, K. J. Barakat, D. R. Wagle, M. S. Manhas and A. K. Bose, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1999, **64**, 5746; (b) B. K. Banik, M. S. Manhas, Z. Kaluza, K. J. Barakat and A. K. Bose, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1992, **33**, 3603; (c) A. K. Bose, B. K. Banik, C. Mathur, D. R. Wagle and M. S. Manhas, *Tetrahedron*, 2000, **56**, 5603; (d) D. Bandyopadhyay, J. Cruz and B. K. Banik, *Tetrahedron Symposium*, 2012, **68**, 10686 (in Print).
- Studies on Beta Lactams. Part 83; For Part 82, see: R. N. Yadav and B. K. Banik, "Modern Chemistry and Applications", 2018, in press. We have not given any part number before. The part number is given here on the basis of publications on beta lactams in which B. K. Banik is an author/co-author/corresponding author.